

ENGINEERED HYBRID TEXTILES REINFORCED FLAT CEMENT BOARD COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This research investigated how hybrid textile-reinforced mortar (TRM) can be engineered for composite boards, through two jute wovens and eucalyptus pulp, and their correlations with matrix: characterization of jute textiles, amount of pulp; the influence of fabric design into matrix; and desizing fabric effects. Molding by slurry dewatering and mechanical properties by four-point bending were performed. Results pointed out F1 has higher opened mesh and lower tensile strength, 7% of pulp is the optimal; both fabrics represented almost similar mechanical properties; and desizing was effective, but flexural stress of TRMs decayed probably due to uneven surface fabrics, which must be improved later in an industrial process.

KEYWORDS: TRM, hybrid composites, fabric design, bonding.

INTRODUCTION

The establishment of fiber-matrix bonding at the interface is a critical parameter in affecting the mechanical properties of cementitious composite, such as stiffness, strength, and ductility (Fidelis et al., 2019). Stress transfer capacity between fiber-matrix is a primary factor characterizing fiber cement composites, which is highly influenced by morphological, chemical constitution, and compatibility (Halvaei, 2021; Jewell et al., 2022).

The strength level of bonding influences the ductility of cementitious composite, thus, the optimal condition is related to an intermediate degree, which means weak enough to enable slippage and yet strong enough to transfer the forces (Fidelis et al., 2019). Low module fibers interfere with increasing the toughness of the composite, mainly related to work dissipated or overall energy absorbed until complete failure (Jewell et al., 2022).

Non-circular and rough shape is a modification of fiber shapes, which can result in the improvement of anchorage and achievement of radial stresses. These alterations can create an active zone of strength, which is determined in the pullout force test (Fidelis et al., 2019). Synthetic fiber has been modify roughness, these are solutions created for physical bonding growth, thus, such as cross-sectional and longitudinal shape changes of propylene fiber are common methods to alter the format to enhance adherence (Halvaei, 2021; Hao et al., 2018). Cellulose fibers already have good compatibility with cementitious matrix, but the fibers require adjustments to guarantee the bonding. Thus, high water absorption capacity of cellulosic fiber hinders, which can will make the bonding ability difficult and, the highly alkaline pH of cementitious matrix degrades the fibers and them affects the composite durability (Li et al., 2021; Liu & Lv, 2021).

Even so, the implementation of cellulosic fibers to reinforce cementitious matrix has been increasing, these fiber reinforcements conduct to an increased energy absorption and ductility mainly because of

the capacity to bend and support loads after the initial cracking (Filho et al., 2020). Dispersed macro and microfibers of cellulose, mainly wood pulp, sisal, Manila hemp, or cotton have a length of between 2 and 10 mm and a diameter of between 10 and 30 μm , these dimensions imply, in general, the better achievement of pulp properties, concerning flexural strength and hardness as compared as other cellulosic fibers (Reixach et al., 2019).

Cellulosic textile-reinforced mortar (TRM) has been employed utilized to be highly ductile, in comparison with synthetic textiles; it is influenced by the crack development stage and progressive failure of the individual yarns (Cevallos & Olivito, 2015; de Carvalho Bello et al., 2019; Homoro et al., 2022; Trochoutsou et al., 2021). According to the bonding aspect, should be considered to textile materials beyond fibers properties, such as longitudinal characteristics (yarns) and geometry disposal (fabric design) (D'Antino & Papanicolaou, 2017). Yarn geometry influences the mortar impregnation degree because the penetration of mortar into yarn cannot be achieved cross-section of its, that can be easier detached, as named as telescopic effect (Birenboim et al., 2021; De Santis et al., 2017; Halvaei, 2021).

The architecture of textile (mesh size and weaving features) influences not only the reinforcement ratio but also the interlock bonding of fiber-matrix. 2D-fabric has shown better bond behavior due to the crossed yarns, concurrently these ligaments can also cause the stress concentrations by crimped geometry, and can increase the possibility of failure (Kohan et al., 2022; Trochoutsou et al., 2021)

Hardwood pulp, as bleached eucalyptus pulp is a typical reinforcement to commercial cementitious boards, it was chosen due to its shorter length and better dispersion capacity within the matrix (Jongvisuttisun & Kurtis, 2015). The chosen process of molding was slurry dewatering, which requires the use of pulp, due to solid retention and, preventing solid parts be sucked by vacuum.

This research aimed to investigate how hybrid textiles can be engineered to reinforce flat cement boards, being two jute architectures of flat wovens and eucalyptus hardwood pulp, and their correlations with cementitious matrix, according to bonding and bridging effects at younger ages by four-point bending. Thus, the experiments targeted to determine: (i) characterization of jute textiles, (ii) optimum amount of eucalyptus pulp; (iii) effect of fabric design (mesh sizes) into cementitious matrix; and (iv) desizing fabric treatment and its effects (fiber and composites).

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Cementitious matrix composition

A fine aggregate cementitious matrix with a maximum size of 19.9 μm and the particle size distribution was evaluated using a laser diffraction particle size analyzer model LA-950 (Horiba, Brazil). Cement type CPV ARI was used as a binder, which contains high initial strength, without mineral addition, it corresponds to Type III according to ASTM C150 (ASTM C150 - 07, 2007). Filler, ground limestone (Itaú, Votorantim, Brazil) is used as a partial substitution for ordinary Portland cement due to its benefit of the physical-mechanical properties and hydration. The maximum size of particle size of the filler is 11.56 μm .

Fibers and textile

Eucalyptus pulp (Suzano, Brazil). The particle density of the pulp was 1.52 g/cm^3 , which was determined using a helium pycnometer, model Ultrapycnometer 1000 (Quantachrome, Brazil). The values of length are ~ 0.73 mm length size and ~ 14.6 μm width according described by Ballesteros et al. (2017) (Ballesteros et al., 2017). The amount of used pulp is shown in **Tab. 1**.

Two Brazilian jute fabrics were used, one more opened mesh - TJ (Juta Castanhal company, Brazil) which was named by Fabric 1 (F1, **Fig. 2a**), and another - DIY (SisalSul, Brazil) Fabric 2 (F2, **Fig.2c**).

Chemical products

H_2O_2 - 50% (Peroxidos do Brasil, Brazil) was diluted to 0.8% (w/v). NaOH was diluted to 0.5% (w/v).

Processing

Treatment of jute fabric

Based on the textile industry process of desizing (starch withdrawal), the continuous method, made in a pad-steam machine, was adapted to the laboratory process, and changed from two steps (treatment and washing) to three steps (treatment 1 and 2 and, washing), because of industry process is a continuous stage of production (Karmakar, 1999). First bath: 0.8% of solution of H₂O₂ at 90°C (neutral pH, 10 min); second bath: 0.5% of solution of NaOH at room temperature (25°C, 10 min); third bath: washing with two baths of deionized water, until neutral pH achievement.

TRM composites production

The amount of eucalyptus hardwood fiber definition was based on previous studies (Ballesteros et al., 2019; Filomeno et al., 2020), which are grounded on the fiber-cement Brazilian industry. Firstly, the ranges of 4, 7, and 10% of pulp with jute TRM were determined and selected by mechanical tests to verify of pulp standard. The amount of ordinary Portland cement and limestone filler varied proportionally in the only first experiment, reducing them when increased the % of pulp (**Tab. 1**). Second, after established pulp standards, the difference between fabric designs (Fabric 1 and 2) was compared and their formulation follows the same pulp standard (7%). Third, the same fabrics were desizing and all TRMs also follow the same formulation (**Tab. 1**).

Table 1: Composites formulation by % mass

Samples	Fabric 1	Fabric 2	Pulp	Cement	Filler
F1_4%P	X		4.00	63.26	30.37
F1_7%P	X		7.00	61.76	28.87
F1_10%P	X		10.00	60.26	27.37
F2_7%P		X	7.00	61.76	28.87
F1_TRAT_7%P		X	7.00	61.76	28.87
F2_TRAT_7%P	X		7.00	61.76	28.87

The TRM composites were produced at a laboratory scale using the slurry-dewatering method followed by pressing, according to Savastano et al. (Filomeno et al., 2020; Savastano et al., 2005). In the process, initially, hardwood eucalyptus pulp was dispersed in water at 3000 rpm for 5 min. The ordinary Portland cement CP V – ARI and limestone were added, and the mixture was stirred at 1000 rpm for 5 min. Part of the mixture was transferred to a casting box, after the fabric was inserted (**Fig. 1a**), the remainder of the mixture was put on top and the negative pressure (80 kPa) was applied to remove the excess water in the process and, hand-densification was used to start the pressure process and compacting (**Fig. 1b**). After this step, the fiber-cement composites were pressed at 3.2 MPa for 5 min (**Fig. 1c**). The composites were cured in sealed plastic bags at room temperature for 1 day and after being cured by thermal curing for 6 days, set at 60°C of temperature and 60% of relative humidity and, 1 day they were immersed in water. For the study, 12 fiber-cement flat plates were produced, with a dimension of 200 mm × 200 mm × 5 mm.

a) Fabric insertion on casting box

b) Handle-densification

c) Pressing (3.2 MPa for 5 min)

Figure 1: Steps of composite production by slurry-dewatering method

Textile characterization

Weight of fabric (g/m²) (ASTM D3776/D3776M – 20, 2020), *count yarn (tex)* (Eq. 1) (ISO 1973:2021, 2021)

$$\text{Count (tex)} = \frac{1000 \times \text{Mass}}{\text{Length}} \quad \text{Eq.1}$$

Pick per inch (PPI) and End per inch (EPI) (ASTM D3775-17, 2017)

The test method covers the measurement of end (warp) and pick (weft) count and is applicable to all types of woven fabrics. It is measured by Magnifying glass tool for textile.

Tensile strength for Textile - Mechanical tests

Tensile Properties of Fabrics by Grab test, to determine maximum load and stressing at maximum load (ISO 13934-1:2013, 2013).

Optical micrography

Digital images of fabrics were obtained by a digital camera connected with biological microscopy (Sony, Color Video Camera ESWAVEHAD, mold 55C-DC93-P), at 63x of magnifications.

Starch visual identification (Iodine solution)

Iodine commercial solution 2% from Farmax was used to reveal visually the starch presence (Saravanan et al., 2012).

Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FTIR)

To verify the functional groups of starch in the samples, after treatment, its remotion, and FTIR spectra were performed for this comparison. Commercial jute fabrics (Fabric 1 2) as control samples and their own desized fabric were compared. FTIR model ALPHA (Brucker®). Values were measured by reflectance and Attenuated Total Reflection (ATR), using zinc selenide, sixty-four scans, wavelength between 4000–400 cm⁻¹ and resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Composite characterization

Mechanical tests - Four-point bending for cementitious composite

The mechanical tests were carried out in a universal testing machine Emic DL-30000, equipped with a 1 kN load cell. The test was performed in a four-point bending flexural, with a span of 135 mm and a deflection rate of 1.5 mm/min. Modulus of rupture (MOR), the limit of proportionality (LOP), modulus of elasticity (MOE), and specific energy (SE) were calculated following Eqs. (2), (3), (4), (5), according with Réunion Internationale Des Laboratoires D' Essais Et Des Recherches Sur les Matériaux Et Les Constructions – RILEM (1984) (Tonoli et al., 2009):

$$MOR = \frac{P_{\text{máx}} \cdot Lv}{b \cdot h^2} \quad \text{Eq.2}$$

$$LOP = \frac{P_{\text{lop}} \cdot Lv}{b \cdot h^2} \quad \text{Eq.3}$$

$$MOE = \frac{276 \cdot Lv^3}{1296 \cdot b \cdot h^2} \quad \text{Eq.4}$$

$$SE = \frac{EA}{b \cdot h} \quad \text{Eq.5}$$

which Pmax is the maximum load, Lv is the distance between upper supports, b and h are the composite width and thickness, respectively, Plop is the load at the upper point of the linear portion of the load-

deflection curve, and m is the tangent of the slope angle of the load vs. deflection plotting in the elastic behavior. The energy was calculated by integration of the area of the load-deflection curve to the point which corresponds to a reduction in the load-carrying capacity of 50% of the maximum reached (Savastano et al., 2000).

The results obtained from physical and mechanical properties were analyzed using statistical software S.A.S 9.3 (Statistical Analysis System) (SAS/STAT® Software). All statistical analyses were performed at a 5% level of significance by the Tukey test, and it was used a random design to compare the means. The variables used for the statistical test were MOR, LOP, MOE, and SE comparing 4, 7, and 10% of pulp with jute fabric of younger ages. Physical tests - Water absorption (WA), bulk density (BD), and apparent void volume (AVV) (bellow) were also performed by the Tukey test.

Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

Images from SEM were prepared without recovering and they were fixed to carbon holders in a stub. SEM equipment (HITACHI brand, TM-3000 model) with a coupled microanalysis system with X-ray energy dispersive spectroscopy was utilized. An acceleration voltage of 16 kV was used, and pictures were obtained by acquisition of backscattered electrons with an increase of x50.

Physical tests

Fiber-cement composites were cut wet into four specimens (160 mm × 40 mm x 5 mm) using a diamond saw cooled with water. Water absorption (WA), bulk density (BD), and apparent void volume (AVV) of fabric-cement composites were obtained, following the procedures described by ASTM C20-00 Equations (6), (7), (8) present how the physical properties were obtained (ASTM C20-00, 2022).

$$WA (\%) = \frac{M_{sat} - M_{dry}}{M_{dry}} \quad \text{Eq.6}$$

$$BD (g/cm^{-3}) = \frac{M_{dry}}{M_{sat} - M_i} \quad \text{Eq.7}$$

$$AVV (\%) = \frac{M_{sat} - M_{dry}}{M_{sat} - M_i} \quad \text{Eq.8}$$

The M_i represents the mass immersed in water; M_{sat} represents a saturated specimen with a dried surface, and M_{dry} the total dry mass of the specimen, after 24 h in an oven at 105°C; and the ρ is the bulk density of the water.

RESULTS

Textile characterization

Figure 2: Visual aspect of two jute architectures of flat wovens

Two analyzed fabrics, Fabric 1 and 2, have different weights ($192 \text{ g/m}^2 \pm 8.5$ and $258 \pm 15.64 \text{ g/m}^2$). Opened mesh (**Fig. 2, Fig. 3, and Tab. 2**) is the distance between two warp yarns (vertical) and two weft yarns (horizontal), which were determined by optical microscopy measurement: Fabric 1 (**Fig. 2a** - warp direction - $2.39 \pm 0.22 \text{ mm}$ and weft direction - $4.20 \pm 0.17 \text{ mm}$) and more closed Fabric 2 (**Fig. 2c** - warp direction - $1.99 \pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$ and weft direction - $2.54 \pm 0.19 \text{ mm}$). Another different parameter took account pick per inch (warp) and end per inch (weft), Fabric 1 (weft direction - 5.5 yarns/inch and warp direction - 8.5) and Fabric 2 (weft direction - 8 yarn/inch and warp 10 yarn/inch). However, despite different parameters presented by two jute fabric, both have similar yarn count of $3.60 \pm 0.14 \text{ tex}$.

Table 2: Two jute fabric characterization (F1 and F2)

	F1	F1	F2	F2
	Warp	Weft	Warp	Weft
Yarn count	$3.60 \pm 0.14 \text{ tex}$	$3.60 \pm 0.14 \text{ tex}$	$3.60 \pm 0.14 \text{ tex}$	$3.60 \pm 0.14 \text{ tex}$
Fabric - tensile strenght	$436.99 \pm 22.45 \text{ N}$	$222.2 \pm 1.61 \text{ N}$	$525.9 \pm 44.2 \text{ N}$	$260.8 \pm 23.3 \text{ N}$
Weight	$192 \pm 8.5 \text{ g/m}$		$258 \pm 15.64 \text{ g/m}$	
Distance yarns	$2.39 \pm 0.22 \text{ mm}$	$4.20 \pm 0.17 \text{ mm}$	$1.99 \pm 0.1 \text{ mm}$	$2.54 \pm 0.19 \text{ mm}$
Pick or End per Inch	8.5 yarns/inch	5.5 yarns/inch	10 yarn/inch	8 yarn/inch

Figure 3: Opened mesh of Fabric 1 and 2, before and after desizing treatment

Since physical presented data (weight, opened mesh, pick or end per inch, and count yarn), Fabric 1 is lighter, more open, and less dense of yarns/inch than Fabric 2, and they also provide differences in mechanical properties. Thus, strength tensile results of Fabric 2 showed achieving higher values than Fabric 1, the maximum force of weft direction 260.8 ± 23.3 and warp - $525.9 \pm 44.2 \text{ N}$ and Fabric 1 $222.2 \pm 1.61 \text{ N}$ and warp direction $436.99 \pm 22.45 \text{ N}$.

Fabric treatments

The desizing treatment with hydrogen peroxide (0.8%) and caustic soda (0.5%) was realized to remove starch and impurities, with a view to improving wettability and adhesion properties (Wang et al., 2019). To discovery the presence of starch, common iodine solution 2% revealed it on a visual test, which can be seen black lines of warp yarn at **Fig. 4b**. Being starch presence in warp yarn, part of the weaving process to increase yarn strength during fabric interlacing (Landage, 2022). Thus, after treatment, to confirm the result, iodine solution was applied again and did not appear more black lines, being evidence that treatment was successful.

To support the treatment another test was carried out by infrared absorption spectrum of FTIR test (**Fig. 4a**), it demonstrates the shifts in the chemical structure of jute fabric, through bands identification and comparison in the spectrum of untreated jute Fabric 2 (red curve) and treated jute Fabric 2 (black curve).

Figure 4: Results of FTIR and iodine solution of untreated and treated jute fabrics

Demarcated bands of interest, which are presented in the **Fig. 4a**, their related functional groups are shown on the **Tab. 2**, in which are highlighted bands: the large majority of treatment modifications are related to pectin and waxy removal (3742, 2900, 1025, and 896 cm^{-1}), besides lignin (1500-1600 and 1249 cm^{-1}) and hemicellulose (1742 cm^{-1}). Particularly, the band of 2900 cm^{-1} corresponds to C-H bonds, it is related to amendment in alcohol and alkane groups in pectin, with the decrease in the absorption band of the groups present in amide to the iodine test (Rajulapati et al., 2020). It is also important to highlight the bands between 3365-3333 are related to the stretching vibration of bonded and unbonded -O-H, that is a great band near 3300 cm^{-1} (Fig. 4a) responsible to absorb water, thus, both spectrums can be seen this.

Table 2: FTIR spectrum information - bands, functional groups, and explanations

Bands (cm^{-1})	Functional Groups	Explanations	References
3742	N-H	Amide group of pectin associated with waxes	(Rajulapati et al., 2020)
2900	C-H	Methylene groups and waxy presence (pectin)	(Dave et al., 2014)
1742	C=O	Stretching vibration in hemicellulose	(Kabir et al., 2013)
1600-1505	C=C and -OCH ₃	Acetyl groups - lignin	(Kundu et al., 2021)
1249	-C-O	Aryl group in lignin	(Kundu et al., 2021)
1025	C-O	Glycosidic linkage of pectin	(Kandimalla et al., 2016)
896	C-H	β -glucosidic linkage in pectin	(Rajulapati et al., 2020)

Composite characterization

The need to use pulp for cementitious composite production by slurry dewatering method, along with use benefit of cellulosic dispersed fiber, due to its capacity to deform and support loads after the initial failure (Filho et al., 2020), then the amount of pulp was a starting point to verify the behavior and synergy with jute textile.

The pulp variation of 4, 7, and 10% (% wt.) with jute Fabric 1 (the biggest mesh size) were applied to reinforce cement matrix and tested by four-point bending to generate comparative data. Three representative graph curves are presented in **Fig.5a**, which show 7 and 10% of pulp could achieve an increase in the flexural strength and specific deformation of both composites, while 4% of pulp presented lower tenacity values. According to Tukey statistics analysis (represented by letters in the

Tab. 3), 7 and 10% of pulp represented the same as statistical data to MOR, LOP and MOE, except for SE that 10% presented a high value (**Fig. 5b**); whereas 4% had almost the least parameters; except for MOE, because low amount of pulp evidence the fragile feature of cementitious matrix, which until first failure the MOE's curves is less inclined, but the tenacity is much lower and, it can be seen at **Fig 5a**. Even so, after the first failure, the rise of pulp amount (7 and 10%) allowed a high capacity for deformation due to the creation of multi-cracking, which can express the curve's range between LOP and MOR, and the specific energy (area of the graph), that are showed their values increase in the **Fig.5a**.

Figure 5: Mechanical composite results of amount pulp comparison with F1 (more opened mesh), according to bending flexure and specific energy.

Table 3: Mechanical tests results (MOR, LOP, MOE and SE) of all samples

SAMPLES	MOR (MPa)	LOP (MPa)	MOE (GPa)	SE (kJ/m ²)
F1_4%P	4.83 ± 0.46 ^b	3.19 ± 0.5 ^a	3.04 ± 0.54 ^a	1.55 ± 0.28 ^c
F1_7%P	5.57 ± 0.27 ^{ab}	2.70 ± 0.34 ^a	2.10 ± 0.23 ^b	2.99 ± 0.37 ^b
F1_10%P	6.10 ± 0.64 ^a	3.01 ± 0.43 ^a	2.16 ± 0.44 ^b	3.61 ± 0.29 ^a
F1_7%P	5.57 ± 0.27 ^{ab}	2.70 ± 0.34 ^a	2.09 ± 0.23 ^a	2.99 ± 0.37 ^a
F2_7%P	5.94 ± 0.32 ^a	2.90 ± 0.37 ^a	1.54 ± 0.32 ^{ab}	3.60 ± 0.35 ^a
F1_TREAT_7%P	4.83 ± 0.52 ^{bc}	2.36 ± 0.53 ^a	1.64 ± 0.45 ^{ab}	2.93 ± 0.40 ^a
F2_TREAT_7%P	4.68 ± 0.49 ^c	2.15 ± 0.66 ^a	1.27 ± 0.23 ^b	3.55 ± 0.63 ^a

*The letters in the same column represent the statistical difference from the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$). The letter "a" for the group with the highest average, followed in decreasing by "b" and at last "c".

For the next experiments, 7% of pulp optimal amount with jute fabric reinforcement for cementitious composites was the standard of formulation, in terms of plats integrity after demolding considering the visual evaluation, and due to almost similar data between 7 and 10% (Tukey test, **Tab. 3**). Thus, new plats and the two architectures of jute textiles - Fabric 1 and 2 (**Fig. 2a and 2c**) were compared, and their representative curves of mechanical composite properties are in the **Fig. 6a**. Both TRMs presented near results, being LOP and SE have values statically equal (Tukey test), MOR presented results almost equal, with minimal prevalence to F2_7%P, which can be influenced by higher specific surface, because the architecture of Fabric 2 is more closed. While MOE values of F2_7%P presented slight lower 1.54 ± 0.32 GPa, and F1_7%P has 2.10 ± 0.23 GPa, despite no significance variance, it occurred due to low curve inclination (**Fig. 6b**) and probably associated to lower insertion of the matrix into the mesh, that it quickly detached, but even, had adherence on the surface and still provoked tenacity.

Figure 6 – Results of four-point bending of treated TRM (F1_7%P and F2_7%P)

The last experiments are related to a comparison between two jute desized fabrics reinforced cementitious composite and untreated fabric composites, this treatment was realized to promote the enhancement of fabric-matrix bonding (Wang et al., 2019). As presented before, the desizing treatment was well-succeeded through iodine and FTIR tests. Two desized TRM and after 8 days were evaluated by four-point bending and data are displayed in **Fig.7**, which demonstrated significant adherence improvement (an increase of the horizontal length of graph when compared to **Fig. 6a**) for both fabrics. LOP and SE performed no significant difference between four formulations of 7% of pulp with untreated and treated jute TRM. When MOE was previously compared (**Fig.6**) presenting F1_7%P slightly superior value, after treatment both fabrics maintained these differences, even getting worse F1_TRAT_7%P – 1.64 ± 0.45 GPa, was slightly superior value than F2_TRAT_7%P – 1.27 ± 0.23 GPa, in which had statistically no significant variance. However, when comparing untreated jute fabrics composites and treated jute, MOR of F2_7%P and F2_TRAT_7%P had significant differences, being treated fabric much lower than untreated, according to Tukey analysis.

Figure 7 – Results of four-point bending of treated fabrics composites

Authors associated the properties reduction of strength and elastic modulus of cellulosic fiber reinforcing cementitious composite due to porosity, which can be caused by insufficient compaction, fiber aggregation, or/and poor fiber/matrix bonding (Baričević et al., 2022; Filho et al., 2020). In this experiment, the shape of treated fabrics was uneven (**Figure 2b and 2d**) and this affects the molding process, which had problems in compaction of treated fabrics into composites, to confirm this low-compaction, SEM images were evaluated. The SEM image of treated TRM interface (**Fig.8b**) shows the presence of more voids between fibers of jute textile, which demonstrates the volume increase of yarns, these analyses were done by comparing with untreated jute TRM composites (**Fig. 8a**). SEM images present well-inserted fabrics into matrix, which can be related to good anchorage and tenacity capacity.

Figure 8 – SEM images of interface jute fabric-matrix composites

Physical tests of different pulp amounts (4,7 and 10%), which 7 and 10 % presented no significant difference between water absorption (%w/w) and apparent void volume (%v/v), only bulk density had a significant difference to 7 and 10%, but the lowest value was 4% of pulp (**Tab. 4**); while the bulk density of 4% presented the highest value, followed by 7 and 10%. Another analyzed group was the difference between untreated and treated jute fabrics (1 and 2) composites, which had the same value, without a significative difference in all composites for water absorption (%w/w) and apparent void volume (%v/v) and, low difference between four samples for bulk density (g.cm^{-3}) (**Tab.4**).

Table 4: Physical tests results (water absorption, bulk density, and apparent void volume) of all tested composite samples reinforced by F1 (higher opened mesh) with 4,7 and 10% of pulp and both designs of jute fabric (F1 and F2) in the untreated and treated conditions.

Samples	Water absorption (%w/w)	Bulk density (g.cm^{-3})	Apparent void volume (%v/v)
F1_4%P	20.07 ± 6.44 ^b	1.55 ± 0.11 ^a	30.61 ± 7.86 ^b
F1_7%P	25.55 ± 0.74 ^{ab}	1.37 ± 0.01 ^b	35.06 ± 0.78 ^{ab}
F1_10%P	29.14 ± 2.35 ^a	1.33 ± 0.04 ^b	38.88 ± 2.01 ^a
F1_7%P	25.55 ± 0.74 ^a	1.37 ± 0.01 ^{ab}	35.06 ± 0.78 ^a
F2_7%P	25.17 ± 2.16 ^a	1.41 ± 0.04 ^a	35.54 ± 2.20 ^a
F1_TREAT_7%P	25.84 ± 7.40 ^a	1.37 ± 0.06 ^{ab}	34.95 ± 8.45 ^a
F2_TREAT_7%P	31.90 ± 6.98 ^a	1.33 ± 0.08 ^{ab}	41.92 ± 7.14 ^a

*The letters in the same column represent the statistical difference from the Tukey test ($p < 0.05$).

The letter “a” for the group with the highest average, followed in decreasing by “b”.

CONCLUSION

Hybrid jute fabric and eucalyptus hardwood pulp were applied in this research to reinforced cementitious flat plates composites, the amount of pulp, the opening of mesh and desizing treatment were each other compared, and some results were pointed out:

- i) Jute textile characterization provided Fabric 1 - F1 with higher opened mesh, lower tensile strength, and lower number of yarns/inch than compared with Fabric 2 – F2, but yarn counts was the same for both fabrics, which denoted similarities as reinforce effects.
- ii) In general, the amount of pulp influenced all mechanical properties (MOR, LOP, MOE, and SE), which the most expressive gain tenacity and absorbed energy. 7% of pulp was considered the optimum degree, due to mechanical properties achieving and processing.
- iii) 2 architectures of jute fabric (mesh sizes) represented almost similar mechanical properties in EE and LOP, but MOR had a minimal prevalence to F2_7%P (7% of eucalyptus pulp and Fabric 2 - more-closed), which can be influenced by higher specific surface and, simultaneously MOE was reduced, probably associated with lower insertion of the matrix into the mesh.
- iv) Desizing treatment was effective, by visual iodine test, that do not revealed black color referent to amide and FTIR spectrum showed the test after desized jute fabrics, and related to amide decreased the bands and, both methods confirmed the efficacy of the treatment. When they were inserted to reinforce the composites, the mechanical bending test revealed that tenacity was improved mainly by the more closed fabric sample (**Fig. 7**). However, flexural stress substantially decayed for both samples, such as MOR values of treated fabrics (**Tab. 3**), influenced by irregularity of fabric and low compaction, which may have caused high porosity and low interface bonding, but it requires further investigation in the future.

Notably, inappropriate fabric processing may have caused the irregularity of treated fabrics, thus, the next step must repeat the fabric treatments in an automated industrial process, with adequate equipment to maintain the width and regularity of fabric.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This article is linked by an approved project of Fapesp/Fapeam (2014/50948-3). The authors gratefully acknowledge the funding by CAPES — “Coordenação de Aperfeiçoamento de Pessoal de Nível Superior” (Grant Number 001) — Brazilian Federal Agency for Support and Evaluation of Graduate Education). We also appreciate the raw materials (cement and limestone) donated by Infibra S/A company.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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